

'Grey literature' in systematic reviews and evidence syntheses on Environmental Health & Toxicology topics: a survey protocol

Abstract

Background

Systematic reviews and other types of evidence syntheses use rigorous methods to identify and synthesise all of the relevant evidence to answer a question. A robust search strategy is crucial to conducting a high quality evidence synthesis, as an inadequate search may miss relevant evidence and produce biased findings. Methodological recommendations endorse searching for 'grey literature,' i.e., reports published outside of traditional commercial publishing. However, there is currently a lack of clarity about what is considered to be the relevant types of grey literature nor how to deal with it.

Objectives

This survey will aim to answer three questions: 1) How do those conducting evidence on environmental health and toxicology (EHT) topics understand 'grey literature'; 2) Where do they search for grey literature?; 3) How do they deal with included grey literature evidence?

Methods

Participants will be individuals who conduct systematic reviews and evidence syntheses in EHT, without restrictions on: previous experience in conducting evidence synthesis, age, gender or geographic location. Survey will be disseminated via relevant professional organisations, systematic review and evidence synthesis organisations, and social media. It will consist of a mix of demographic and content questions. Descriptive statistics will be reported as frequencies and percentages; free-text responses will be analysed thematically.

Ethics

The survey was exempted from a requirement to undergo ethics review. The first page of the survey will provide the respondents with information about the project and ethics approval; respondents will provide consent by clicking on a button to advance to the survey.

Keywords

Systematic review; evidence synthesis; gray literature; environmental health; toxicology

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Introduction

Systematic reviews and other evidence syntheses, such as systematic maps and scoping reviews, use rigorous methods to find and synthesise all of the evidence that answers a question of interest. They are integral to evidence-based decision making, informing decisions ranging from individual patient-clinician encounters to population- or country-level policies.(1)

The conduct and publication of systematic reviews in particular has exploded in the past 25 years, from approximately one systematic review published per day in 2000, to over 100 per day by 2020.(2) This is especially evident in healthcare – the Cochrane Library currently lists over 7500 reviews on healthcare-related topics – but the conduct and publication of systematic reviews and other types of evidence syntheses is also rapidly growing in other areas. These areas include, for example, toxicology and environmental health,(3), social sciences including law,(4) education,(5) and policing.(6) This trend is also evident in the establishment and growth of topic-specific databases of systematic reviews and other types of evidence syntheses, including the International Database of Education Systematic Reviews (containing over 275 systematic reviews); the World Health Organisation’s repository of systematic reviews on interventions in environment, climate change, and health (containing over 1000 systematic reviews); and the Campbell Collaboration (containing over 240 systematic reviews across social interventions, business, climate, crime and justice, education, and other topics).

A key factor affecting the quality of an evidence synthesis is the robustness of its search strategy.(7) This is because inadequate searches may miss relevant evidence and therefore produce biased findings.(8) The Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions (hereafter ‘the Cochrane Handbook’) and the Methodological Expectations of Cochrane Intervention Reviews (MECIR) manual provide detailed guidance for conducting Cochrane systematic reviews on the effects of healthcare interventions.(9, 10) The Cochrane Handbook recommends that robust searches include: health-related bibliographic databases (MECIR Standard C24, mandatory) and specialist bibliographic databases if applicable (MECIR Standard C25, highly desirable); ongoing studies and unpublished sources; trial registers (MECIR Standard C27, mandatory); regulatory agency sources and clinical studies reports; and ‘grey literature’ (MECIR Standard C28, highly desirable). (9, 10)

~~While some of these resources are not necessarily pertinent to evidence syntheses in the fields of environmental health and toxicology, these recommendations illustrate expectations to go beyond bibliographic databases when conducting a review, including~~
~~g~~Grey literature, ~~is~~ defined as “reports published outside of traditional commercial publishing,” including dissertations and conference abstracts (Cochrane Handbook section 4.3.5). ~~Approaches to searching the grey literature include internet searches, hand searching, checking reference list of included studies and relevant reviews.~~(9)

Resources that are specific to environmental health and toxicology adopt a similar understanding of ‘grey literature’ to that found in the Cochrane Handbook. For example, the US Environmental Protection Agency’s (EPA’s) *Generic TSCA [Toxic Substances Control Act] Systematic Review Protocol with Chemical-Specific Methodologies* defines grey literature similarly broadly, as “sources not found in standard, peer-reviewed literature

databases, [including] white papers, conference proceedings, technical reports, reference books, dissertations, information on various stakeholder websites and various databases.”(11) US National Toxicology Programme’s Handbook for Conducting a Literature-Based Health Assessment Using OHAT [Office of Health Assessment and Translation] Approach for Systematic Review and Evidence Integration, similarly considers grey literature to be those “publications that are not commercially published or are not readily available to the public.” Examples of grey literature, include: technical reports from government agencies or research groups (e.g. Environmental Protection Agency, Food and Drug Administration, Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry), working papers from research group or committees, and white papers.(12)

~~Whilst grey literature searches are recommended, these recommendations are not always implemented. For example, one study found that only 49% of systematic reviewers of clinical trials reported searching grey literature as part of their reviews. The situation is likely similar or perhaps worse in other areas that do not have as long a history of utilising systematic reviews, including toxicology and environmental health. This may be because the diverse nature of grey literature can be challenging to search, there are no ‘gold standard’ search methods for grey literature, there is an abundance of grey literature material, and time and resource constraints impose limitations on how comprehensively reviewers may search.(13) This is a concern, however, as failing to search for grey literature may lead to missing important evidence and biased findings.(13)~~

The Cochrane Handbook’s approaches to searching for grey literature include internet searches, hand searching, checking reference list of included studies and relevant reviews.(9) The methods for conducting systematic reviews and evidence syntheses on topics other than healthcare are often adapted from the Cochrane Handbook’s methods.(3, 5, 14) The Conduct of Systematic Reviews in Toxicology and Environmental Health Research (COSTER) recommendations cover the key practices for systematic reviews in toxicology and environmental health research. Similar to the Cochrane Handbook, COSTER recommends searching key databases (Recommendation 2.1), searching sources of grey literature (Recommendation 2.2), checking reference lists (Recommendation 2.4), and contacting relevant individuals and organisations (Recommendation 2.5). Relevant organisations could include, for example, those found in the EPA’s Systematic Review Protocol (Appendix E.2), which provides a list of 24 websites which can be used to conduct grey literature searches in environmental and human health hazard topic areas – including government websites of relevant departments from Australia, Canada, US and others, databases of toxicological, chemical and hazardous profiles of substances, risk assessments, and others.(11) US National Toxicology Programme’s Handbook similarly provides a list of seven websites under the grey literature category, which include Theses and Dissertation databases, and open access repositories.(12)

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similar or perhaps worse in other areas that do not have as long a history of utilising systematic reviews, including toxicology and environmental health. This may be because

While searching and potentially including grey literature in evidence syntheses is recommended, the challenges associated with doing so have long been recognised. Some of these challenges include: the diverse nature of grey literature can be challenging to search, there are no the absence of 'gold standard' search methods for grey literature, there is an abundance of grey literature material, heterogeneity in type of grey literature, the size (e.g. page counts) of grey literature documents, difficulty in accessing grey literature, difficulty in analysing credibility of some sources, paucity of centralised sources, inaccurate bibliographic information (e.g. authorship, publication dates), duplication, requirement for distinct search strategies across different resources, and time and resource constraints which impose limitations on how comprehensively reviewers may search.(13) This is a concern, however, as failing to search for grey literature may lead to missing important evidence and biased findings.(13, 15-18)

Despite the grey literature searching recommendations from COSTER a range of sources, it is not currently clear how what reviewers conducting evidence syntheses on environmental and health topics (EHT) deal with grey literature in practice. It is not clear what they consider to be the relevant types and sources of grey literature. Not nor is it clear how the reviewers deal with grey literature in their evidence syntheses – particularly, given the many challenges associated with doing so. To broaden our understanding of these issues, we will therefore conduct a survey to identify:

1. How do those conducting evidence syntheses on EHT topics understand 'grey literature' – what types of evidence do they regard as 'grey literature'?
2. Where do they search for grey literature?
3. How do they deal with grey literature evidence included in their evidence syntheses?

The answers to these questions will be descriptive – that is, they will identify what *are* the current practices of those conducting evidence syntheses on EHT topics. If a considerable breadth of approaches is identified in terms of understanding, searching, and dealing with grey literature, a follow-up project will be conducted, to establish consensus on what those practices *should be*.

Methods

A protocol for this survey was prepared a priori. There is currently no reporting checklist for survey protocols, however, the completed survey and its findings will be reported following the Checklist for Reporting Results of Internet E-Surveys (CHERRIES) reporting guideline.

Respondents

Survey participants will be individuals who conduct systematic reviews and other evidence syntheses on EHT topics – for example, systematic reviewers or evidence synthesisers, search specialists, librarians, other methodologists, etc. There will be no restrictions imposed on respondents' experiences in conducting previous evidence syntheses – that is, respondents who are novices through to very experienced will be included as participants – although their level of experience will be queried in the survey. There will be no restrictions imposed on the age, gender, or geographic location of respondents. However, given that the questions target professional practices, it is anticipated that the respondents will be over 18 years old.

Survey dissemination

We will adopt a multi-pronged approach to reach target respondents.

Survey dissemination will be conducted via approaching professional organisations with a request to disseminate the information about the survey and a link to their membership. These will include organisations in EHT (e.g., the Society of Toxicology, [Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry](#), [Toxicology Forum](#), [Academy of Toxicological Science](#), [International Society for Environmental Epidemiology](#)); library and search specialist organisations (e.g., the Medical Library Association in the USA, the European Association for Health Information and Libraries in Europe, the Chartered Institute of Library and Information Professionals in the UK, Health Libraries Australia, etc.); systematic review and evidence synthesis organisations (e.g., GRADE Working Group, Cochrane, the Campbell Collaboration, JBI, etc.); and social media (e.g., X, Instagram, LinkedIn, etc.).

We will contact organisations by email, with a letter introducing the survey and a request to disseminate it to their members. The letter will provide information about the project and its aims and a web link to the survey.

We will disseminate this same information about the survey via personal and institutional social media accounts, with weekly reposts.

The survey will be open for four weeks (following the publication of the protocol).

Survey instrument

The survey will be administered online and hosted using Qualtrics or JISC Online Surveys.

The survey instrument will consist of both demographic and content questions. The demographic questions will query the geographic locations of respondents and their prior levels of experience in conducting systematic reviews in EHT. The content questions will aim to establish what the respondents consider to be grey literature in the context of conducting EHT systematic reviews and other evidence syntheses, where they search for grey literature, and how they treat grey literature in their systematic reviews and evidence syntheses. The survey will consist of a mix of tick-box and free-text questions to enable

respondents to provide a full range of details in their answers. The full survey instrument is provided in Appendix A.

As the survey will be brief, there will be only one version of the survey, with the sequence of questions held constant. Respondents will be able to return to prior answers to change them if they wish to do so.

Survey testing

To test for technical and comprehension issues and to generate an estimate of the time required to complete the survey, we will pilot the survey with two colleagues not involved with the project. Based on the feedback received, the survey will be adjusted prior to dissemination if needed.

Analyses

Both completed and partially completed surveys will be included in the analysis. Excel and/or STATA will be used for quantitative data analysis. Descriptive statistics will be reported as frequencies and percentages. Data permitting, we will calculate the differences in proportions between respondents based on participant characteristics, e.g., different geographic locations, and level of experience including years of experience in contributing to evidence syntheses and the type of employer.

Free text responses will be coded by two authors and analysed thematically.⁽¹⁹⁾ The process will occur in several stages. One author will immerse themselves in all of the free-text responses received to a question, and create preliminary codes based on examination of the data (inductive approach) – stage 1. The preliminary list of codes will then be revised (e.g. amalgamated, de-duplicated) – stage 2. The responses to the question will then be coded using the revised codes – stage 3. The coding will be reviewed by the second author, and recoded where required – stage 4. Finally, both coders will jointly evaluate the recoding (e.g. suitability of any added or removed codes, whether a code has been appropriately applied), and make any revisions required to finalise the coding by consensus – stage 5. The process will be repeated for other questions with free-text responses. Coding will be conducted using the software available to the authors, e.g. NVivo or Excel.

We intend to make both quantitative and qualitative data available, however, where required to protect the respondent's anonymity, identifying information in free-text responses will be de-identified. For example, if a name of an individual or an institution is included by a respondent, this will be replaced by “[personal name]” or “[institutional name]” in the text. Visualisations of the findings will be prepared using Tableau and/or R.

Data availability

Data sharing is not applicable to this [article-survey protocol](#) as no new data were created or analysed in this study.

Ethics approval and informed consent

Project details were reviewed by the Secretariat of the University of Oxford Medical Sciences Interdivisional Research Ethics Committee (MS IDREC), which determined that ethics review was not required to conduct the proposed survey.

The first page of the online survey will provide brief information about the project, project team, ethics approval, data protection, and consent. Respondents will provide their consent by clicking on the “if you consent, please click next to proceed” button. Participation and completion of the survey will be voluntary and anonymous. No incentives for survey completion will be offered.

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